

SOLAR OPERATED COWSHED

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ABSTRACT

In this project we focus on solar equipment's that saves the energy and economy of solar powered equipment's for Indian farms and farmers. Solar system is used for farms basically for irrigation system which runs without battery that saves battery cost and battery maintenance cost. Automation of cow shed using solar irrigation system is economic project for farmers and dairy farms in this unit solar panel of 40watts is used for generation of electricity which is supplied to dc electric motor for water pumping. This motor lifts water from water well and supplied to storage located on cowshed this water is drawn in the shed for various purpose like floor cleaning shower for animals for body temperature control and for biogas. Remaining water from storage is supplied to farm plots by using drip irrigation system and excess electricity generated by solar panel is used for farmer's house as an inverter.